

DEVELOPMENT OF A PHYTOCHEMICAL-ENRICHED TOPICAL GEL FOR DIABETIC WOUND CARE

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ABSTRACT

Background

Wound healing is a complex biological process involving inflammation, proliferation, and tissue remodeling. The development of herbal formulations that enhance these processes without cytotoxic effects is of increasing interest, particularly for diabetic wound management where healing is often impaired. This study investigates the phytochemical composition, physicochemical characteristics, and biological efficacy of a polyherbal wound-healing gel containing Quercetin and Gallic acid.

Methods

Phytochemical screening of the herbal extracts was conducted to identify major bioactive constituents. The polyherbal gel formulations (F1–F5) were prepared using a Carbopol-based matrix and evaluated for physicochemical parameters including color, appearance, pH, spreadability, homogeneity, viscosity, and extrudability. Biological efficacy was assessed using MTT cytotoxicity and in-vitro wound scratch assays. The MTT assay determined cell viability at various concentrations of Quercetin, Gallic acid, and their combination, while the wound scratch assay evaluated the effect on cell migration.

Results

Phytochemical analysis confirmed the presence of steroids, carbohydrates, proteins, anthocyanin's, phenols, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, and flavonoids. All formulations demonstrated desirable physicochemical attributes, with pH values between 7.5 and 7.8, good spreadability, homogeneity, and extrudability, and viscosities ranging from 1210 to 1308 centipoise. MTT assay results showed IC_{50} values above 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}$, indicating no significant cytotoxicity. The wound scratch assay revealed a dose-dependent enhancement of cell migration, suggesting improved wound-healing potential. Statistical analysis confirmed the significance of these effects ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The polyherbal gel formulations displayed excellent physicochemical stability and significant biological activity, highlighting their potential as effective wound-healing agents. These findings suggest promising therapeutic application, particularly in diabetic wound management. Further *in-vivo* and molecular investigations are warranted to elucidate the mechanisms of action and confirm clinical relevance.

KEYWORDS: *Herbal gel, Quercetin, Gallic acid, MTT assay, Wound scratch assay, wound healing*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder marked by sustained hyperglycemia, which contributes to various complications, including delayed or impaired wound healing. [1]. Diabetic patients frequently develop chronic wounds like diabetic foot ulcers, which are difficult to treat and often result in infections, amputations, or mortality [2]. The delayed wound healing in diabetes is attributed to reduced cellular proliferation, impaired angiogenesis, decreased collagen synthesis, and increased oxidative stress and inflammation [3]. Medicinal plants are rich in bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential and have been extensively explored for wound management [4]. Polyherbal formulations, which combine multiple plant-derived constituents, offer synergistic effects, minimal side effects, and cost-effectiveness [5]. These formulations enhance various physiological processes involved in wound repair, including inflammation, tissue formation, and remodeling [6]. Among the many bioactive phytochemicals, quercetin and Gallic acid are particularly notable for their wound-healing potential. Quercetin, a flavonoid found in fruits and vegetables, possesses antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties that promote cell proliferation, migration, and angiogenesis [7, 8]. Gallic acid, a phenolic compound found in tea, grapes, and berries, exhibits strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities that support tissue regeneration [9,10]. Combining these two compounds in a polyherbal gel formulation may enhance wound-healing efficacy through complementary mechanisms [11]. The gel base, typically composed of natural polymers such as Carbopol, ensures sustained release and prolonged therapeutic activity at the wound site [12]. The study aims to develop and assess a polyherbal gel formulation containing Quercetin and Gallic acid, assessing its phytochemical composition, physicochemical properties, and biological efficacy using MTT and wound scratch assays. The proposed formulation offers a promising, natural, and safe alternative for managing diabetic wounds and improving patient outcomes [13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Extract

The polyherbal extract was obtained as a gift sample from Pune, India. All other chemicals and reagents employed in the study were of analytical grade and obtained from NICE Chemicals, Kerala.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Qualitative phytochemical analysis of the polyherbal extract was performed using standard procedures to identify the presence of various phytoconstituents, including steroids, carbohydrates (Molisch's and Benedict's tests), proteins (Xanthoprotein and Ninhydrin tests), anthocyanin, phenols, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, and flavonoids [14,15]. The results were used to confirm the phytochemical profile of the extract.

FTIR Analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed to determine the functional groups and verify the chemical constituents of the polyherbal extract. The spectra were obtained within the wavelength range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} using an FTIR spectrometer. The characteristic absorption peaks obtained represented the molecular vibrations corresponding to specific functional groups, serving as a molecular fingerprint for the sample [16].

Formulation of Herbal Gel Containing Quercetin and Gallic Acid

The herbal gel was formulated using Carbopol 934 as the gelling agent. The measured amount of Carbopol 934 was gradually dispersed in distilled water and magnetically stirred at 120 rpm for 30 minutes to achieve complete and uniform hydration. In a separate beaker, methyl paraben and triethanolamine were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water, while propylene glycol was separately blended with another 10 mL of distilled water. The methyl Paraben–Triethanolamine solution was added slowly to the hydrated Carbopol dispersion with gentle stirring to form a uniform gel base [17]. An herbal drug solution containing 10 mg each of Quercetin and Gallic acid dissolved in 2 mL of ethanol was incorporated into the gel base with continuous mixing (Table 1). Finally, the propylene glycol solution was incorporated into the prepared gel base, and the mixture was gently stirred until a smooth and homogeneous gel was formed. [18].

Table 1. Formulation Composition of Herbal Gel (F1–F5)

Ingredients	F1 (1%)	F2 (1.5%)	F3 (2%)	F4 (2.5%)	F5 (3%)
Carbopol 934 (g)	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30
Herbal Drug (Quercetin: Gallic acid, 1:1)	10 mg each				
Methyl Paraben (g)	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
Triethanolamine (mL)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Propylene Glycol (mL)	5	5	5	5	5
Distilled Water	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.
Total Weight (g)	10	10	10	10	10

EVALUATION OF THE HERBAL GEL

Colour, Appearance, and Homogeneity

The prepared polyherbal gels were visually inspected for colour, appearance, and homogeneity after setting in containers. The formulations were observed for the presence of aggregates or particulate matter [19].

Measurement of pH

The pH of each formulation was measured by dispersing 1 g of gel in 10 mL of distilled water and allowing it to stand for 2 hours. Measurements were taken three times using a calibrated digital pH meter, and the average value was recorded. [20]

Spreadability

Spreadability was evaluated using a glass slide and wooden block apparatus based on slip and drag characteristics. Two slides were used with 2 g of gel placed between them. After placing a 1 kg weight on the sample for 5 minutes, the upper slide was pulled with an 80 g weight, and the time (T) taken for it to move a distance of 7.5 cm was recorded.

$$S = M \times L / T \quad S = TM \times L$$

Where S = spreadability, M = weight (g), L = distance (cm), and T = time (s). A lower T indicates better spreadability [21].

Viscosity

Viscosity was measured at 25 °C using a Brookfield viscometer (DV-III programmable rheometer) at speeds ranging from 10–100 rpm with 30 s intervals between readings [22].

Extrudability

Each formulation was filled into collapsible aluminum tubes and secured between two glass slides. A 500 g weight was then placed on the slides, and the extruded gel was collected and weighed. Extrudability was categorized as follows: >90% – excellent, >80% – good, and >70% – fair. [23].

In-Vitro Drug Release

Drug release studies for formulations F3–F5 were conducted using a Franz diffusion cell equipped with a cellophane membrane and phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as the receptor medium, maintained at 37 ± 1 °C. Aliquots of 1 mL were withdrawn at predetermined intervals up to 5 hours and analyzed spectrophotometrically. [24].

MTT ASSAY

Preparation of Reagents and Materials

MTT reagent (filtered through a 0.2 µm membrane) was stored at 2–8 °C for short-term use or frozen for long-term storage. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), a CO₂ incubator, microplate reader, inverted microscope, and refrigerated centrifuge were used for the assay [25].

Preparation of Test Solutions

Serial two-fold dilutions of the test samples ranging from 3.125 to 100 µg/mL were prepared using the culture medium. [26].

Cell Lines and Culture Conditions

Vero cell lines were procured from NCCS (Pune, India) and cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin (100 IU/mL), and streptomycin (100 µg/mL). The cells were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂ until confluence was achieved. [27].

Procedure

A cell suspension containing 1×10^5 cells/mL was seeded at 100 µL per well in a 96-well plate and incubated for 24 hours to allow partial monolayer formation. The medium was then replaced with 100 µL of the test sample at varying concentrations and incubated for an additional 24 hours. Following incubation, the medium was removed, and 20 µL of MTT solution (2 mg/mL in PBS) was added to each well, followed by incubation for 4 hours at 37 °C. The supernatant was then discarded, and 100 µL of DMSO was added to dissolve the formed formazan crystals. The absorbance was recorded at 570 nm using a microplate reader. [28].

% viability = Sample abs /Control abs x 100.

IN-VITRO WOUND SCRATCH ASSAY

Vero cells (2×10^5 cells/well) were seeded into 6-well plates and incubated at 37 °C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere for 24 hours. A uniform scratch was created across the cell monolayer using a sterile P200 pipette tip. The detached cells were gently rinsed off with PBS, and the wells were treated with test samples at concentrations of 6.25 µg/mL and 12.5 µg/mL in serum-free DMEM. Untreated cells served as the control. Images were captured at 0 and 24 hours using a phase-contrast microscope at 10× magnification. The percentage of wound closure was calculated as described in [29]. All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and the results were statistically analyzed.

Wound closure (%) = Measurement at 0 h - Measurement at 24 h / Measurement at 0 h x 100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR Interpretation of Quercetin

The FTIR spectrum of Quercetin confirmed the presence of major functional groups characteristic of flavonoids. Broad O–H stretching vibrations observed at 3411.12 cm⁻¹ and 3325.86 cm⁻¹ confirmed the presence of hydroxyl functional groups. The phenolic O–H bending appeared at 1382.96 cm⁻¹ [30]. A prominent absorption band at 1665.80 cm⁻¹ was attributed to the aromatic or aryl ketonic (C=O) stretching vibration. Aromatic C=C stretching vibrations were detected at 1610.91, 1562.63, and 1522.70 cm⁻¹. The in-plane C–H bending appeared at 1320.17 cm⁻¹, while out-of-plane bending bands were seen at 941.25, 822.32, 678.09, and 602.65 cm⁻¹ [7]. The absorption band at 1263.35 cm⁻¹ was assigned to C–O stretching in the aryl ether ring, while the band at 1200.63 cm⁻¹ corresponded to phenolic C–O stretching. The peak at 1168.93 cm⁻¹ represented the characteristic stretching and

bending of C–CO–C bonds in ketones [9]. These bands confirm the presence of functional groups consistent with pure Quercetin [10].

Fig 1- FTIR Spectrum of Quercetin

FTIR Interpretation of Gallic Acid [34]

The FTIR spectrum of Gallic acid exhibited distinct peaks characteristic of its polyphenolic structure. A sharp absorption at 1708 cm⁻¹ corresponded to the C=O stretching of the carboxylic acid group. Bands observed at 1624.55 cm⁻¹ and 1449.17 cm⁻¹ were attributed to aromatic C=C stretching, while the band at 1245.65 cm⁻¹ represented C–O–H stretching. Peaks at 2856.65 cm⁻¹ and 2927.46 cm⁻¹ corresponded to aromatic C–H stretching vibrations. Broad absorptions at 3297.35 cm⁻¹ and 3376.25 cm⁻¹ were associated with O–H stretching, confirming the presence of hydroxyl groups. The broad band between 2500–3500 cm⁻¹ indicated overlapping O–H and C=O stretching of carboxylic acid functionalities. Additionally, a distinct peak at 1542.94 cm⁻¹ was assigned to phenolic O–H stretching. These spectral features collectively confirmed the presence of characteristic functional groups in Gallic acid.

Fig 2- FTIR Spectrum of Gallic acid

FTIR Interpretation of Formulation F5 (3%)

In formulation F5, Carbopol 934 was used as the gelling polymer. The IR spectrum of the gel showed a broad peak between 2500–3500 cm⁻¹, with a strong O–H stretching vibration at 3357.88 cm⁻¹. The absorption band at 1644.07 cm⁻¹ represented C=O stretching of the polymer. Peaks at 2852.82 cm⁻¹ and 2928.19 cm⁻¹ corresponded to C–H stretching vibrations. The observed peaks were similar to those of pure Carbopol, Quercetin, and Gallic acid, with no significant shifts or disappearance of major functional groups. This suggests the absence of any chemical interaction between the active constituents and the polymer, confirming their compatibility within the formulation. [35, 36]

Fig 3- FTIR Spectrum of Formulation F5 (3 %)

Phytochemical analysis of the extracts showed the presence of major secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, tannins, phenols, and saponins, confirming the existence of bioactive compounds that contribute to wound-healing activity. [37, 38]. These inferences provide valuable insights into the chemical composition of the substances tested and contribute to understanding their properties and potential applications. Various organoleptic characters of the wound-healing herbal gel are shown in Table 2.

Table 2-Evaluation of herbal gel

Parameters	F1 (1%)	F2 (1.5%)	F3 (2%)	F4 (2.5%)	F5 (3%)
Colour	Yellow to Brownish Green	Yellow to dark green	Greenish Yellow	Pale yellow	Light pale yellow
Appearance	Smooth & Translucent	Smooth & Translucent	Smooth & Translucent	Smooth & Translucent	Smooth & Translucent
Surface pH	7.5	7.69	7.7	7.76	7.8
Spreadability	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
Homogeneity	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous	Homogenous
Viscosity	1210	1215	1248	1276	1308
Extrudability	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good

Physicochemical Evaluation of Herbal Gel (Formulation F5)

The extracts of Quercetin and Gallic acid exhibited a free-flowing consistency with a characteristic odour. The prepared gels showed a smooth, uniform texture and light brown coloration. The pH range (7.5–7.8) indicates suitability for topical application, ensuring no skin irritation upon use [39]. The viscosity of the formulations increased proportionally with the concentration of Carbopol 934, ensuring adequate consistency and ease of application [40]. Spreadability and extrudability were rated as good for all formulations, indicating desirable rheological behavior—essential for patient compliance and uniform application over the wound surface [41]. The uniform distribution of the active constituents within the gel matrix suggests homogeneity and stability of the formulation [42]. The presence of bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids and phenolic acids contributes to the gel's antioxidant and wound-healing properties [43]. Medicinal plants are known for their rich phytochemical profiles, which confer antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and tissue-regenerative potential [44]. All five formulations (F1–F5) exhibited acceptable physicochemical characteristics. Among them, Formulation F5 (3%) showed optimal viscosity, pH, and spreadability, making it the most suitable for further *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluations [45].

MTT ASSAY

Fig 4: Calibration curve showing the % Viability against the concentration for the different the extracts and the formulation F5 (3%)

MTT Assay

The cytotoxicity of the optimized herbal gel formulation (F5), containing Quercetin and Gallic acid (1:1 ratio) with 3% Carbopol 934, was evaluated by the MTT assay. Serial dilutions ranging from 3.125 µg to 100 µg/ml were tested, and the results were compared against untreated control cells after 24 hours of incubation [46]. The IC_{50} values for Quercetin alone, Gallic acid alone, their combination, and formulation F5 (3%) were all greater than 100 µg/mL, indicating that none of the samples exhibited cytotoxic effects on Vero cells within the tested concentration range. These findings suggest that the test samples did not significantly reduce cell viability or proliferation, confirming the biocompatibility and non-toxic nature of the formulation at concentrations suitable for wound-healing applications [47,48]. The absence of cytotoxicity implies that the formulated herbal gel can safely be used for topical applications without causing adverse effects on normal skin cells, thereby supporting its potential suitability for wound-healing purposes [49].

In Vitro Wound Scratch Assay

The scratch assay was performed to evaluate the cell migration ability of the prepared herbal formulation, an essential parameter for assessing wound-healing potential [50]. Confluent monolayers of Vero cells were scratched with a sterile pipette tip to create a wound-like gap, followed by treatment with test samples at concentrations of 6.25 µg and 12.5 µg in serum-free DMEM. Untreated wells were used as controls [51]. Images of wound closure were captured using a phase-contrast microscope at 0 and 24 hours, and the percentage of wound closure was quantified [52]. After 24 hours of incubation, the treated groups showed a marked increase in wound closure compared to the control. The closure percentage was dose-dependent, with 12.5 µg showing a higher rate of migration than 6.25 µg [4]. The enhanced migration of Vero cells indicates that the formulation promoted cell proliferation and motility, both of which are essential processes in re-epithelialization during wound repair [53]. Statistical analysis revealed that the observed effects were significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the herbal formulation effectively promoted cell migration and wound closure. These results suggest that Quercetin and Gallic acid, owing to their potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, act synergistically to enhance cellular mechanisms involved in the wound-healing process [54].

Discussion

Wound healing is a dynamic process involving inflammation, proliferation, and tissue remodeling [55]. The ability of the test formulation to enhance cell migration without cytotoxicity underscores its therapeutic promise. Quercetin is reported to modulate growth factor expression and collagen synthesis, thereby promoting fibroblast proliferation and extracellular matrix remodeling, while gallic acid contributes through free radical scavenging and anti-inflammatory activity that reduces oxidative stress at the wound site [56, 57]. Their combination within a Carbopol-based gel matrix provides a sustained and biocompatible delivery system conducive to dermal regeneration [58, 59]. Collectively, the MTT assay confirmed the non-toxic nature of the formulation, while the scratch assay

demonstrated its efficacy in promoting wound closure through enhanced cell migration [60, 61]. Hence, the herbal gel formulation containing quercetin and gallic acid shows significant potential as a safe and effective topical therapeutic agent for wound healing. Further investigations, including in vivo wound models and molecular mechanism studies, are warranted to validate these preliminary findings and explore clinical applicability.

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